

Study of Algal Diversity from Sina Kolegaon Dam

Sachin S. Chavan¹ & Tejas D. Garad²

Department of Botany,

S.G.R.G Shinde Mahavidyalaya, Paranda. Dist. Dharashiv(MS)

Corresponding Author – Sachin S. Chavan

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Abstract

Algae is one of the most diverse groups of living organism that are distributed in all across the oceans, rivers, ponds and lakes. Algae play an important role in maintaining aquatic ecosystem and form the base of food chain or food web. Algae are classified as Rhodophyta (red algae), Phaeophyta (brown algae) or Chlorophyta (green algae) depending on their nutrient, pigments and chemical composition. They are considered as a source of bioactive compounds as they are able to produce a great variety of secondary metabolites with some also a valuable food resource too. Some of the algae are also been known to be pollution indicator and help in reduction of industrial pollutants in rivers and other water sources. The present study was aimed to assess the microalgal diversity of water in Sina kolegaon dam. Dam/lakes are the important water resources & used for several purposes. The water quality of all fresh water environments is assessed by the physico-chemical & biological parameters. The present investigation is focused on the water quality and diversity of algae. The dam water is extensively used for drinking & irrigation purposes. Today the production of oxygen by algae is another reason for saying “Our lives depend on algae”. Given the photosynthetic ability of algae, they are one of the major focuses for sustainable biofuel production & CO₂ consumption. With the above contribution of algae, an attempt was made to diversify the algae species that are in and around Sina Kolegaon dam and document the presence of valuable algal species. A total of 18 algal species were partially identified namely Spirogyra, Oedogonium, Euglena Sanguine, Cyanobacteria, Oscillatoria, Chamydomonas, Mougeotia, Auxospore, Chroococcus minor, Chlorophyta and Oedogonium areolatus species are found.

Keywords: Ecosystem, Metabolites, Biofuel etc.

Introduction:

In Marathwada region there are many dams, lake on different rivers, but less attention has been paid to presence of algae in water. In present project the Sina- Kolaegaon dam is near the paranda which is 15 kms from paranda. Mandayam Osuri Parthasarathy Iyengar (15 Dec. 1886-10 Dec.1963) was a prominent Indian botanist. He is known as “Father of algology in India”. The term alga (Latin-Seaweeds) was first introduced by Linnaeus in 1753, meaning the Hepaticae. Alga are aquatic, plant like

organism. The Alga can be categorized into 7 types- each are distinct sizes, functions, color, the different divisions are Euglenophyta (Euglenoids), Chrysophyta (Golden-brown algae & Diatoms), Pyrrophyta (fire algae), Chlorophyta (Green algae), Rhodophyta (Red algae), Phaeophyta (Brown algae), Xanthophyta (Yellow green algae) Sina-Kolegaon Dam, is an earthfill dam on local river Sina near Paranda town of Dharashiv district from Maharashtra state.

Material and Methods:**Collection of Samples:**

To study algal biodiversity of Sina Kolegaon Dam, 6 different sites of backwater located in Paranda tehsil area of Dharashiv district have been selected. Algal samples were collected from different sites from 02 Dec. 2025 to 10 Feb 2026. Acid washed collection bottles were used for collection of algal samples. Firstly observed the dam and area occupying by water. first going on light house which is made in water and observe all surrounded water standing on it because it made in between the water and take photos of dam water for project collection. Water samples were collected from each side of dam for collection. Water samples were collected at morning section. Samples were collected from corners, edges or shadow places of dam water where greenish water is present therefore easily algae are found in samples. Floating, Planktonic submerged and attached epiphytic algal samples were collected separately in collection bottles.

Identification and Preservation of Algae Samples:

Firstly, collected samples cleaned, solid particles are removed from sample and samples preserved in refrigerator for further study. Each sample were collected in a separate bottle and labelled like spot-1, spot-2, spot-3 etc. Some thread like green part seen in water which is first collected in glass and then transfer in the sample bottle for collection. Yellowish green part also seen on the stone/rocks which also collected in sample bottle. Identification of the algae samples

were carried out mostly through microscopically. Fresh as well as preserved algal forms were observed thoroughly under research microscope and identified with the help of standard literature on algae like Plant Diversity Laboratory Manual by Asst. Prof. Dr. Ismail Eker.

Results and Discussions:

The study in different water bodies of Sina-kolegaon Dam showed a rich diversity of filamentous algae belonging to varies classes. The different site were also containing a large number of micro-algae, flagellated phytoplankton and diatoms. Some of the algae that were identified during the course of study are *Spirogyra*, *Oedogonium*, *Euglena Sanguine*, *Cyanobacteria*, *Oscillatoria*, *Chlamydomonas*, *Mougeotia*, *Auxospore*, *Chroococcus Minor*, *Micrasterias*, *Macrandrous*, *Pediastrum tetras*, *Closterium cornu*, *Euglenagracils*, *Phacusonyx*, *Trachelomonasallia*, *Stigeoclonium* and *Gloeocapsa* etc.

Conclusion:

Algae are integral part of the ecosystem that serves for various purposes such as fodder, photosynthesis and also as waste management. Sina-Koleagon dam is one of the most drinking water sources for Kolgaon, Kaundaon, Donja, gaon and other neighbour villages. A rich source of various forms of filamentous algae, therefore study on such algae can play an important role in ecological management and also in keeping a check on the pollution level in the water bodies.

Table No.1: Enlisted Algae from Study Area

Sr. No.	Name of the algae	Study Stations					
		S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6
	Class: Zygnematophyceae Order: Zygnematales Family: Zygnemataceae						
1.	<i>Spirogyra</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
2.	<i>Mougeotia</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
	Class: Zygnematophyceae Order: Desmidiaceae Family: Desmidiaceae						
3.	<i>Micrasterias</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
	Family-Closteriaceae						
4.	<i>Closteriumcornu</i>	+	-	+	+	-	+
	Class: Euglenida Order: Euglenales Family: Euglenaceae						
5.	<i>Euglena sanguine</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
6.	<i>Euglena gracilis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
	Family-Phacaceae						
7.	<i>Phacusonyx</i>	+	+	+	+	-	-
	Class: Chlorophyceae Order: Oedogoniales Family: Oedogoniales						
8.	<i>Oedogonium</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
	Family: Oedogoniaceae						
9.	<i>Macrandrous</i>	+	+	-	+	+	+
	Order: Chlamydomonadales Family: Chlamydomonadaceae						
10.	<i>Chlamydomonas</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
	Family-Chaetophoraceae						
11.	<i>Stigeoclonium</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
	Order: Sphaeropleales Family: Hydrodictyaceae						
12.	<i>Pediastrumtetras</i>	+	+	+	+	-	+
	Class: Cyanophyceae Order: Chroococcales Family: Chroococcaceae						
13.	<i>Chroococcusminor</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
14.	<i>Gloeocapsa</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
	Order: Oscillatoriales Family: Oscillatoriaceae						
15.	<i>Oscillatoria</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
	Class- sericytochromatia						
16.	<i>Cyanobacteria</i>	+	-	+	-	+	+
	Class- Bacillariophyceae						
17.	<i>Auxospore</i>	-	+	+	+	+	-
	Class: Euglenida Order-Euglenales Family: Euglenaceae						
18.	<i>Trachelomonasallia</i>	+	+	-	+	+	+
+ means present - means absent							

Table:2: Collection site

Sr. No	Sample No.	Collection Site of Dam
1	S1	South
2	S2	South
3	S3	West
4	S4	West
5	S5	North
6	S6	North

Sina kolegaon dam view

Sample collection point

Plate.No.1: Diversity of Algal specimen from Sina Kolegaon Dam

1. Spirogyra

2. Oedogonium

3. Euglena Sanguine

4. Cyanobacteria

5. Oscillatoria

6. Chlamydomonas

7. Mougotia

8. Auxospore

9. Choococcus Minor

Plate.No.2: Diversity of Algal specimen from Sina Kolegaon Dam

18. *Gloeocapsa*

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